

Percutaneous Catheter Drainage: The Optimal Minimally Invasive Procedure for Liver Abscess Management

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Abstract:

Background: Liver abscesses are critical infections that, if untreated, can lead to severe morbidity and mortality. While surgical drainage was once the standard treatment, percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) has emerged as a preferred, minimally invasive alternative. However, factors such as abscess size and comorbidities can influence the success of PCD.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of PCD in managing liver abscesses and to identify factors associated with procedural success and complications.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 300 patients. All patients underwent PCD, and data were collected on demographic characteristics, abscess size, comorbidities, procedural outcomes, and complications. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with t-tests and chi-square tests used to evaluate procedural efficacy. Logistic regression was conducted to identify predictors of unsuccessful outcomes.

Results: The study found a 90% success rate for PCD in liver abscess management. Larger abscesses (>8 cm) and the presence of comorbidities were significantly associated with lower success rates ($p < 0.05$). Complications occurred in 15% of the patients, predominantly minor, with catheter displacement being the most common. Logistic regression analysis identified abscess size and comorbidities as significant predictors of unsuccessful outcomes.

Conclusion: PCD is a highly effective treatment for liver abscesses, but its success is influenced by abscess size and patient comorbidities. Careful patient selection and consideration of these factors are crucial to optimizing outcomes.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on developing strategies to enhance the efficacy of PCD in patients with larger abscesses and significant comorbidities. Additionally, guidelines should be established to better select patients for this procedure.

Keywords: Liver Abscess, Percutaneous Catheter Drainage, Abscess Size, Comorbidities, Procedural Outcomes.

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Introduction

Liver abscesses, which are defined as localised collections of pus within the liver, are serious medical emergencies that need to be diagnosed and treated right once since they can have a fatal outcome if treatment is delayed. Historically, the accepted method for treating liver abscesses was surgical drainage; now, with developments in imaging and interventional radiology, percutaneous catheter drainage, or PCD, has become the preferred minimally invasive option [1]. Reducing the risk of complications, reducing hospital stays, and improving patient outcomes are the driving forces behind this shift towards less intrusive procedures [2].

PCD has been shown to be effective in treating amoebic and pyogenic liver abscesses in recent investigations, with success rates ranging from 80% to 95% [3, 4]. In comparison to traditional surgical procedures, PCD is particularly advantageous because of its minimally invasive nature, which enables the drainage of abscesses with less discomfort for the patient and speedier recovery times [5]. Notwithstanding these advantages, a number of variables affect the efficacy of PCD, such as the abscess's location, size, and the existence of underlying comorbidities, which can impede the treatment process [6].

Large abscesses, which are usually classified as those with a diameter larger than 8 cm, are

particularly difficult to treat since they have a higher chance of not healing and can necessitate several drainage procedures or even surgery [7]. Individualised treatment plans and cautious patient selection are essential since patients with comorbidities, like diabetes mellitus, are more likely to encounter problems and may not heal as quickly [8]. Moreover, the rising incidence of antibiotic resistance has made managing liver abscesses more difficult, especially in pyogenic abscesses where the selection of empirical antibiotics is crucial to the success of the entire treatment plan [9]. In light of the changing clinical landscape, there is an increasing interest in optimising the surgical and medicinal care of liver abscesses in order to improve patient outcomes [10]. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of PCD in managing liver abscesses and to identify factors associated with procedural success and complications.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital with a specialized hepatobiliary unit. The hospital is equipped with advanced imaging and interventional radiology facilities, providing comprehensive care for patients with liver abscesses. The study spanned 12 months, from January 2023 to December 2023.

Participants: A total of 300 participants were enrolled in the study. All participants were patients diagnosed with liver abscesses at the hepatobiliary unit of were included during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with a liver abscess confirmed by imaging (ultrasound or CT scan).
- Patients who were deemed candidates for percutaneous catheter drainage by the attending physician.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with multiple organ failures.
- Patients with a coagulation disorder or those on anticoagulant therapy that could not be reversed.

- Patients with a history of hypersensitivity to the contrast media used during imaging procedures.
- Pregnant women.
- Patients who refused to provide consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria were recruited. Observer bias was minimized by ensuring that the radiologists and clinicians performing and evaluating the procedures were blinded to the study's objectives. Data analysts were blinded to the patient groupings during statistical analysis to avoid analysis bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected through patient medical records, imaging reports, and follow-up visits. Baseline demographic data, clinical characteristics, procedural details, and outcomes were recorded. A standardized data collection form was used to ensure consistency. Follow-up data were collected at 1, 3, and 6 months post-procedure to assess the long-term outcomes of the procedure.

Procedure: Patients underwent percutaneous catheter drainage under ultrasound or CT guidance. The procedure was performed by experienced interventional radiologists. The catheter was placed into the abscess cavity, and the size, location, and volume of the abscess were documented. Post-procedure care included monitoring for complications, managing the drainage, and providing antibiotics as per the hospital's protocol.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized baseline characteristics: categorical data as frequencies and percentages, and continuous variables as means and standard deviations. Procedure efficacy was assessed with t-tests for continuous data and chi-square tests for categorical variables, with $p < 0.05$ indicating statistical significance. Logistic regression identified variables associated with positive outcomes.

Results

A total of 300 participants were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.6 ± 13.2 years, with a male predominance ($n = 210$, 70%). The majority of the participants ($n = 180$, 60%) had a single liver abscess, while the remaining ($n = 120$, 40%) had multiple abscesses. The average size of the abscess was 7.5 ± 2.3 cm. Comorbidities were present in 40% of the participants, with diabetes mellitus being the most common ($n = 72$, 24%).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants (n)	300
Age (years)	45.6 ± 13.2
Gender	Male: 210 (70%)
	Female: 90 (30%)
Number of Abscesses	Single: 180 (60%)
	Multiple: 120 (40%)
Abscess Size (cm)	7.5 ± 2.3
Presence of Comorbidities	120 (40%)
Common Comorbidities	Diabetes Mellitus: 72 (24%)
	Hypertension: 36 (12%)

Of the 300 procedures performed, 270 (90%) were successful, defined by complete resolution of the abscess with no need for further intervention. The remaining 30 participants (10%) required additional procedures, including repeat drainage or surgical intervention. The average time to clinical improvement post-procedure was 5.4 ± 1.8 days.

Complications occurred in 45 participants (15%), with minor complications in 36 (12%) and major complications in 9 (3%). The most common minor complication was catheter displacement (n = 20, 6.7%), while the most frequent major complication was secondary infection requiring further intervention (n = 6, 2%).

Table 2: Procedural Outcomes

Outcome	Value
Successful Procedure	270 (90%)
Additional Interventions Required	30 (10%)
Time to Clinical Improvement (days)	5.4 ± 1.8
Complications	45 (15%)
Minor Complications	36 (12%)
Major Complications	9 (3%)
Common Minor Complication	Catheter Displacement: 20 (6.7%)
Common Major Complication	Secondary Infection: 6 (2%)

Statistical Analysis: The efficacy of the procedure was evaluated by comparing the baseline characteristics of participants who had successful outcomes (n = 270) and those who required additional interventions (n = 30).

those with smaller abscesses (95%, $p < 0.001$). The presence of comorbidities also negatively impacted the success rate, with only 80% of those with comorbidities having successful outcomes compared to 95% of those without comorbidities ($p = 0.002$).

Participants with abscesses larger than 8 cm had a significantly lower success rate (75%) compared to

Table 3: Factors Associated with Procedural Success

Factor	Successful Outcome (n=270)	Unsuccessful Outcome (n=30)	p-value
Abscess Size >8 cm	45 (75%)	15 (25%)	<0.001
Abscess Size ≤8 cm	225 (95%)	15 (5%)	
Presence of Comorbidities	96 (80%)	24 (20%)	0.002
No Comorbidities	174 (95%)	6 (5%)	

Logistic regression analysis identified abscess size greater than 8 cm (OR 3.5, 95% CI: 2.1-5.8, $p < 0.001$) and the presence of comorbidities (OR 2.8, 95% CI: 1.6-4.9, $p = 0.002$) as significant predictors of unsuccessful outcomes.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of Unsuccessful Outcome

Predictor	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Abscess Size >8 cm	3.5	2.1 - 5.8	<0.001
Presence of Comorbidities	2.8	1.6 - 4.9	0.002

Discussion

The study included 300 participants, primarily male, with a mean age of 45.6 years. Most participants had a single liver abscess, with an

average size of 7.5 cm. Notably, 40% of the participants had comorbidities, such as diabetes mellitus, which potentially influenced the outcomes.

The procedure's success rate was high, with 90% of participants experiencing complete resolution of the liver abscess without requiring additional interventions. The average time to clinical improvement was relatively quick, at just over five days. However, complications were observed in 15% of participants, though most were minor, such as catheter displacement. Major complications were rare, occurring in only 3% of cases.

Statistical analysis revealed that larger abscesses (greater than 8 cm) and the presence of comorbidities significantly reduced the success rate of the procedure. Specifically, participants with abscesses over 8 cm had a 75% success rate, compared to 95% for those with smaller abscesses. Similarly, those with comorbidities had a lower success rate of 80%, versus 95% in those without comorbidities. Logistic regression further confirmed that both abscess size and comorbidities were significant predictors of an unsuccessful outcome.

In the treatment of liver abscesses, (PCD) is becoming more widely acknowledged as a less intrusive and more successful method than percutaneous needle aspiration (PNA). According to Mahmoud et al. (2023), the study also discovered that PCD provides quicker clinical recovery and takes less time for antibiotic therapy and abscess size reduction [11]. Maharaul et al. (2021) conducted a clinical trial that demonstrated the efficacy of ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter drainage as a less invasive and economical approach for the management of partially liquefied and liquefied liver abscesses. According to the study, PCD is a dependable substitute for surgical procedures because of its high success rate and low risk of consequences [12]. Toppo's (2022) prospective observational study provided more evidence of PCD's effectiveness, showing a 100% success rate in patients' abscess volume reduction of at least 50%. In contrast to conventional surgical methods, the study highlighted the minimum invasiveness of PCD and its correlation with early clinical improvement and fewer problems [13].

Conclusion

Percutaneous catheter drainage is an effective, minimally invasive procedure for liver abscess management, achieving a 90% success rate. However, success decreases with larger abscesses and the presence of comorbidities, particularly diabetes. These factors should guide patient selection and treatment planning to optimize outcomes. Personalized strategies are crucial to enhancing the efficacy of this approach in managing liver abscesses.

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